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Importance Assigned by Students and Teachers to Soft Skills: The Case of a Two-Year Technical College

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ABSTRACT

Soft skills play a central role in engineering and technology education, and their importance is expected to increase within the Industry 4.0 framework. However, while the literature covers the soft skills of engineering program graduates, the research focusing on the soft skills required of graduates of a two-year technical college is very limited. In view of this gap, the study described in this paper examines the importance assigned by students and teachers to soft skills required of a two-year technology program graduate. Forty-four electronics students and thirteen electronics teachers from a two-year college took part in the study, which used both quantitative and qualitative instruments. According to the findings, the importance assigned by the students to soft skills was significantly lower than the importance assigned by their teachers. It might be possible to explain the findings by the current curriculum not putting sufficient emphasis on providing relevant soft skills.

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1 INTRODUCTION

"Industry 4.0" is the fourth industrial revolution, after its predecessors that were characterized by water and steam power-based mechanization (first revolution), electricity-based mass production (second revolution) and computer-based automation (third revolution). The current revolution is based on Cyber-Physical Systems, Internet of Things and Big Data [1].

The implementation of the Industry 4.0 concept requires, inter alia, to provide workers with an appropriate qualifications set that includes technical as well as soft skills [2]. Technical skills are abilities that can be taught and that are relatively easy to measure, such as the use of software. On the other hand, soft skills refer to interpersonal qualities that permit the individual to function well in society and achieve his/her goals, such as communication and self-directed learning skills [3]. It should be emphasized that soft skills play a central role in engineering and technology education even today, and their importance is expected to increase within the Industry 4.0 framework [4].

While the literature extensively deals with the soft skills of engineering program graduates, the research focusing on the soft skills required of graduates of a two-year technical college is very limited [5]. Therefore, this study investigated the importance assigned by Israeli electronics students and teachers to the soft skills required of a two-year technology program graduate. To the best of our knowledge, such an analysis was performed here for the first time. It should be noted that most of the students at Israeli two-year technical colleges are from the socioeconomic periphery or attain relatively low academic achievements [6-7].

2 SOFT SKILLS IN ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION

As mentioned above, soft skills are a collection of interpersonal qualities that permit the individual to function well in society and achieve his/her goals [3]. These skills can be implemented in a broad context and are not limited to a particular type of activity [8]. In the engineering and technology context, soft skills include, among other things, effective teamwork and efficient oral and written communication [9].

Recognizing the necessity of soft skills, the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) has updated the accreditation criteria of engineering and technology programs, so as to include soft skills alongside technical skills [9]. Consequently, leading educational institutions, such as University College London (UK) and Purdue University (US), have begun emphasizing the importance of soft skills [10]. However, it is quite difficult to find the appropriate balance in the curriculum between the weight of technical skills and soft skills, and there is still a gap between university training and the industry's requirements [11].

3 RESEARCH GOAL AND METHODOLOGY

The study characterized the importance assigned by electronics students and teachers to the soft skills required of a two-year technology program graduate. Forty-four second-year electronics students (with an average age of twenty years) and

thirteen experienced electronics teachers (with an average age of fifty years) from a two-year college in Israel took part in the study.

The participants completed a closed-ended anonymous questionnaire. It was a five level Likert-like scale ranging between "very important" and "not important at all". The questionnaire covered the soft skills defined by ABET as the qualifications required of a two-year technical college graduate, i.e., (i) a commitment to continuous improvement, (ii) an ability to engage in self-directed learning, (iii) a commitment to address professional and ethical responsibilities, (iv) an ability to function effectively as a member of a technical team, and (v) an ability to apply written and oral communication in both technical and non-technical environments [9]. The questionnaire was validated by two engineering education experts and five students who did not take part in the study.

An importance index was defined as the average of the importance ratings of the five above-mentioned qualifications. This index, ranging between 1 and 5, was calculated separately for the students and their teachers.

Additionally, semi-structured interviews were held with students (five interviews) and teachers (five interviews), who had given their consent to be interviewed as part of the study. The participants were asked, inter alia, whether the current curriculum put sufficient emphasis on providing soft skills. The qualitative data underwent conventional content analysis.

4 FINDINGS

The mean value of the students' importance index was $M = 4.08$ with $SD = 0.49$, while the mean value of the teachers' index was $M = 4.43$ with $SD = 0.35$. The gap, in favor of the teachers, was statistically significant ($t(55) = 2.36, p < 0.05$).

In order to identify the factors leading to the above gap, *Fig. 1* displays the mean importance score of each of the five skills (students and teachers), and *Table 1* presents the corresponding effect sizes. The findings indicate a zero effect size with regard to communication skills, and medium effect sizes with regard to the remaining qualifications.

Fig. 1. Mean importance scores.

Table 1. Effect sizes.

Skill	<i>d</i>
Continuous improvement	0.55
Self-directed learning	0.56
Professional & ethical responsibilities	0.57
Teamwork	0.48
Written & oral communication	0

The qualitative information extracted from the interviews with the teachers indicates that the current curriculum does not reflect the need to provide the students with relevant soft skills:

"This [providing soft skills] is not built into the curriculum... It depends on each teacher and his or her method."

A similar insight seems to be formed by the students' answers in the interviews:

"It can be said that [in the program] there is no focus on teamwork... There is no [focus on] independent learning, and no focus on expressive abilities either."

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

It was found that the overall importance assigned by the students to soft skills was significantly lower than that of the teachers. Indeed, the students and their teachers agreed concerning the importance of effective written and oral communication, but the gap associated with the remaining qualifications was characterized by a medium effect size.

It might be possible to explain the findings by the current curriculum not putting sufficient emphasis on providing relevant soft skills. This fact did not permit the teachers to dedicate the necessary time to these topics that they viewed as very important, and this could have possibly affected the importance assigned to these qualifications by the students. It should be noted, however, that the above imbalance in the curriculum is characteristic of many educational institutions, and is one of the causes for the gap between the training provided by them and the industry's requirements [10-12].

In light of these results, we recommend to revise, where needed, the curriculum of two-year technical colleges so as to dedicate sufficient time to providing the students with soft skills. One of the suggested instruments for developing these qualifications is integrating "real-life" problems into the curriculum [13]. Our recommendations are validated in view of the central role played by soft skills in engineering and technology education, especially within the Industry 4.0 framework [4].

The main limitation of the study is a relatively small number of participants. Therefore, in order to increase the findings' trustworthiness, both quantitative and qualitative tools were applied. In a future study, we will considerably increase the number of participants and examine similar programs.

REFERENCES

- [1] Schwab, K. (2016), *The 4th industrial revolution*, Crown Business, New York.
- [2] Motyl, B., Baronio, G., Uberti, S., Speranza, D. and Filippi, S. (2017), How will change the future engineers' skills in the Industry 4.0 framework? A questionnaire survey, *Procedia Manufacturing*, Vol. 11, pp. 1501-1509.
- [3] Robles, M. (2012), Executive perceptions of the top ten soft skills needed in today's workplace, *Business Communication Quarterly*, Vol. 74, pp. 453-465.
- [4] Cotet, G. B., Balgiu, A. B. and Zaleschi, V. C. (2017), Assessment procedure for the soft skills requested by Industry 4.0., *MATEC Web of Conferences*, Vol. 121, pp. 07005.
- [5] Stewart, M. (2017), Student perceptions of soft skills as an indicator of workplace success, Creighton University.
- [6] Gero, A., Zoabi, W. and Sabag, N. (2014), Animation based learning of electronic devices, *Advances in Engineering Education*, Vol. 4(1), pp. 1-21.
- [7] Gero, A. and Zoabi, W. (2014), Computer animation and academic achievements: Longitudinal study in electronics education, *International Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 30(5), pp. 1295-1302.
- [8] Newell, D. (2002), The smarter they are the harder they fail, *Career Development International*, Vol. 7, pp. 288-291.
- [9] Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (2018), Criteria for accrediting engineering programs, ABET.
- [10] Byrne, Z. S., Weston, J. W. and Cave, K. (2018), Development of a scale for measuring students' attitudes towards learning professional (i.e., soft) skills, *Research in Science Education*, pp. 1-17.
- [11] Kirschenman, M. D. (2011), Improvements to the culture and attitudes in civil engineering education, *Leadership and Management in Engineering*, Vol. 11, pp. 223-225.
- [12] Siller, T. J., Rosales, A., Haines, J. and Benally, A. (2009), Development of undergraduate students' professional skills, *Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice*, Vol. 135, pp.102-108.

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- [13] Gero, A., Stav, Y. and Yamin, N. (2016), Increasing motivation of engineering students: Combining "real-world" examples in a basic electric circuits course, *International Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 32(6), pp. 2460-2469.